

Ecuadorian HECAP Groups Input to the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure (LASF4RI)

Thematic Area: Other (National road map)

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Abstract

This document is a general summary of the aspirations and plans of the different Ecuadorian groups in HECAP. It states the current situation of the large-infrastructure experiments in which the country is currently involved, as well as plans to continue engaging in research activities in these areas and in the development and innovation in the associated fields of engineering. The document will also serve as a contribution to the LASF4RI initiative.

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1 Introduction: overview of the Ecuadorian community

Ecuador is one of the smallest countries in Latin America. However, with nearly 17 M people living in an area of nearly $285 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$, it is the most densely populated nation in South America. High Energy Physics, Cosmology, Astroparticle Physics (HECAP) and related fields have not been historically an essential ingredient of its scientific landscape. In the last decade or so, however, a somehow controversial reform on higher education in the country triggered an extraordinary interest in these fields of knowledge by attracting foreign trained local scientists and foreign professionals in the area. It has also motivated the training of several students in the field at the BSc, MSc and Ph.D. level. Some of these professionals have traveled abroad for such purpose but could be returning to the country in the following years.

About 5 of the approximately 60 institutions for higher education in Ecuador are now involved somehow in HECAP: Escuela Politécnica Nacional (EPN) in Quito, Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo (ESPOCH) in Riobamba, Universidad de Cuenca (UCuenca), Universidad San Francisco de Quito (USFQ), and Yachay Tech University (YTU) in Urcuquí, near the city of Ibarra.

HECAP developed differently in Ecuador compared to neighboring countries. Individual experimental efforts, like the successful and still ongoing participation of Prof. Bruce Hoeneisen in the D0 experiment [1], which dates back to the early 1990s, appeared even before any theoretical contributions. Today, Ecuadorian groups are also part of two large international collaborations: the CMS Experiment [2] at the LHC (EPN, USFQ) and the KM3NeT Experiment [3] at the Mediterranean Sea (YTU). There is also involvement in one regional large-scale effort: the LAGO Project [4] (EPN, USFQ, ESPOCH). In addition, Ecuador has active scientists working in other related fields as theoretical cosmology, relativity and gravitation.

Ecuador is attempting to build scientific tradition in HECAP, still from individual efforts, but with expectations to consolidate well established groups and a solid road map that will route future generations of scientists.

Training is a key element in this strategy. The LA-CoNGA Physics [5] project, an alliance for building capacity in advanced physics in Latinamerican institutions under the umbrella of European Union Erasmus+ program, is a current example of the joint efforts in the region. Many others have preceded it; a highlight is the CLASHEP (Cern Latin American School of High Energy Physics) in 2015, which was held in Ibarra.

November 2020 comes with a great responsibility and reward for Ecuador since the XIII SILAFAE, the largest Latinamerican Symposium of High Energy Physics will take place for first time ever in the country.

In this document we try to delineate a simple but clear strategy for the following 10 to 30 years in the field. Such a plan will serve as a starting point for the younger scientists and as input to the current Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure (LASF4RI) initiative. We believe there is an untapped potential in our youth, which, with the right motivation and support, could help solve some of the deepest mysteries of the universe and boost the frontline technological developments in our region.

2 Scientific context

The spectacular discovery of the Higgs boson in 2012 by the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) collaborations, ATLAS and CMS, marked the completion of the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics. It is maybe the most dramatic example of the power of human ingenuity as its existence was predicted long before its discovery.

But not only man-made accelerators qualify as unique tools to explore the intensity, energy

and cosmic frontiers in our Universe. Cosmic accelerators have also allowed groundbreaking discoveries. The finding of the first extragalactic neutrino source (TXS 05006+056 Blazar) in 2018 by the IceCube Observatory, for instance, targets a new era in our comprehension of the world, crossing the SM, its building blocks and interactions, and the evidence of physics beyond it.

The SM is a very simple quantum field theory that is able to explain a broad range of phenomena over many orders of magnitude. However, we know it needs to be expanded or recast in order to properly describe observations in the cosmological and astrophysical domains as well as to address known theoretical tensions with apparently fundamental, guiding principles. An instance of the latter is the “unnatural” wide range of masses shown by the basic constituents of the SM. On the other hand, the overwhelming evidence of the presence of dark matter and dark energy (cosmological constant) in the universe or the predominance of matter over antimatter in it are just examples of a large list of unsolved mysteries at cosmological scales whose understanding could be linked to high energy particle physics.

Many well-established and beautiful theoretical ideas have emerged in order to tackle the limitations of the SM. To test them, several machines have been built over the last decades. Experiments at Brookhaven’s Alternating Gradient Synchrotron, the Budker Institute in Novosibirsk, CERN’s Proton Synchrotron, Intersecting Storage Rings, and Super Proton Synchrotron, Fermilab’s Tevatron and Main Injector, HERA at DESY, the Japan Proton Accelerator Research Complex (J-PARC), the Stanford Linear Collider, LEP, flavor factories at Beijing, Cornell, DESY, Frascati, KEK, and SLAC have pushed forward much of the current knowledge [6].

In addition, of crucial importance have been many other non-accelerator-based experiments, like those for direct detection of dark matter [7] and facilities analyzing astroparticles emerging from natural sources. Among the latter, experiments as FERMI-LAT [8] and HESS [9], the latest optimized for Very-High-Energy gamma-ray astrophysics, have released a lot of valuable data of cosmic origin, widening the comprehension of hadronic(mostly)/leptonic mechanisms on matter on the high energy component of the electromagnetic spectrum. Data and simulations sets collected by FERMI-LAT and HESS for about 20 years also opened the gate for the era of “Multi-messenger Astronomy and Astrophysics”. They brought significant information about astrophysical neutrinos. Their origin, for instance, can be directly linked to the presence of high-energy hadronic particles. Observation of a spatial and temporal correlation of neutrinos and gamma-rays points towards a joint emission region able to accelerate hadronic particles (most favored scenario). In this sense, good spatial and time resolution among observatories working as a real-time and global alert system network, are crucial. HESS has been working closely with the major operative neutrino observatories in the world with a remarkable lifetime: IceCube [10] (southern hemisphere) and ANTARES [11] (northern hemisphere).

The apparent lack of new results from the LHC, the most powerful and complex man-made accelerator to date, and the several “hints” of beyond-the-SM physics from the other mentioned experiments, seem to indicate the end of a theory-driven field. It is notorious the extraction of valuable data carried by cosmic messengers or astroparticles, and space-time perturbations. Thanks to the greatest technological developments of space- and earth-based facilities, our understanding of the universe has been enhanced by looking to the sky; the so-called “cosmic connection” is now better comprehended. We are maybe entering a phase in which direct experimentation will guide our theoretical ideas. Over the last decades, it has been the other way around, of course. Therefore, it is more important than ever to think about the next generation of large-scale infrastructures.

The painstaking study of sub-atomic particles, like the Higgs boson, could give hints of the nature of the universe at the TeV energy scale. The LHC and its experiments will keep playing a fundamental role in trying to answer profound questions like, is there only one Higgs particle?, does the Higgs couple to all leptons/quarks?, is the Higgs field the only source of fermion masses?, etc. In this regard, the already-approved project, the high luminosity

LHC (HL-LHC), will be a necessary upgrade to complete some of these tasks.

Astroparticles (photons, cosmic rays, neutrinos) and space-time perturbations (gravitational waves), forming the so-called “multi-messengers”, are capable to address several fundamental questions being answered gradually, at a certain level of accuracy (e.g. uncertainty of fluxes as one of the main systematics). Basic questions like the origin and mechanisms of dark matter and energy, black holes, cosmic rays, neutrinos and gravitational waves may only be answered by the intersection of astrophysics (low, medium, and high energy), theoretical physics, particle physics and cosmology: Astroparticle Physics in our current context. In this regard, the construction and operation of large and complementary facilities, as the KM3NeT observatory, are of vital importance.

Future projects [12] include the possibility of e^+e^- colliders like the ILC in Japan and CLIC-380 at CERN, the high energy LHC (HE-LHC), the Future Circular Colliders initiative at CERN, etc., but also experiments that are already moving forward at J-PARC and FERMI-LAB. In the intensity frontier, the latter Lab has taken a role as a world leader. Projects like the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) [14], which will help answer some of the still most fundamental questions about the nature of elementary particles, are already being developed. Similar initiatives, like the P2O project [13], a proposal to direct a neutrino beam from Protvino towards the KM3NeT/ORCA detector, would complement and expand such efforts.

Other future (or upgraded) promising experiments addressing fundamental questions in the intensity and cosmic frontier are PAO [15], CTA [16], DARWIN [17], XENONnT [18], NEXT [19], etc. In Latin-America, the LAGO project, an offspring of PAO, combines the ability to study GRBs with the capability of serving as a space weather instrument. LAGO has played a crucial role into attracting and training many students in the region. Finally, the ANDES [20] laboratory in South-America, with the main objective of studying dark matter and neutrino physics, will become one of the main hubs for particle physics in the region.

3 Objectives

Ecuadorian groups seek to address and help unravel some of the most fundamental questions in physics, as well as to acquire the know-how and expertise on the field of advanced technologies and further applications. Due to our limited size, we cannot possibly tackle every outstanding problem there is, but would like to focus in certain particular domains, which align with the expertise of currently involved scientists. Our objectives in the medium/long term are:

- To continue studying the properties of the Higgs boson.
- To continue using the Higgs boson as a portal to search for new physics.
- To contribute to the search of new phenomena, specially dark matter searches.
- To study the properties of the elusive neutrino particles and their natural sources.
- To get immersed in emerging fields, like multi-messenger astronomy and astroparticle physics, to study cosmological events with the aim of understanding the universe as a whole, i.e., in close connection to our high energy particle physics contingent.
- To help develop and build particle detectors and calibration systems, mainly in the photonic (light sources and sensors) and positioning (acoustic waves and sensors) technology.
- To help develop computing tools for fundamental physics research.
- To train the next generation of physicists in the field but also the next generation of engineers, who can benefit from using HECAP as a leverage to push the frontiers of technology in different areas.

4 Methodology

Due to individual interests and efforts, Ecuadorian groups are now part of

- one international multi-purpose collider experiment at the **energy frontier**: CMS at the LHC (collider physics and instrumentation).
- one international neutrino experiment (**intensity frontier**): KM3NeT (neutrino physics, astroparticle physics and instrumentation).
- and one regional experiment (**cosmic frontier**): LAGO (astroparticle physics and instrumentation).

Without wanting to restrict the scientific creativity and independence of our scientists, neither going backset on global science drivers (joint efforts on funding, common scientific goals, technology development and infrastructures), but based on the experience of other countries in the region and the still limited local manpower, we believe that future groups in particle physics should try to align, as much as possible, to the efforts that are already going on in the country as shown above. We also consider as imperative the need to establish new groups (or expand current theoretical ones) that can join at least one large international collaboration in astroparticle physics and/or multi-messenger astronomy. Such group(s) would close the circle of the experimental efforts in HECAP in the country.

For the medium/long term future of HECAP in Ecuador, we consider it very important to join at least one new large scale international effort in each frontier as well as one new regional one in any frontier. This is because we deem of great importance to build emblematic projects in the Latin American region in order to boost interest and the expansion of the field. Therefore, our methodology and strategy to accomplish the objectives mentioned in the last section can be summarized as follows:

- Keep working in the CMS experiment at the LHC and contribute to the generation of knowledge in collider particle physics (mainly higgs physics, dark matter searches and new phenomena), detector building and engineering.
- Continue contributing to the upgrades of the CMS experiment towards the HL-LHC [21] phase.
- Motivate the expansion of groups working in the CMS experiment.
- Keep working in the KM3NeT experiment and contribute to the generation of knowledge in neutrino physics, astroparticle physics, detectors, related technologies, engineering and further applications.
- Continue contributing to the upgrades and new developments for current and next phases in KM3NeT, i.e., Phase I-II-III, including Super ORCA and aside projects as P2O.
- Motivate the expansion of groups working in the KM3NeT experiment.
- Keep working in the LAGO project with emphasis of developing low cost particle detectors which can help train the next generation of scientists.
- Prepare to join and join one future collider experiment in the energy frontier, like the ILC, FCC [22], etc.
- Prepare to join and join one future experiment in the intensity frontier, for instance DUNE and/or P2O.
- Prepare to join and join one main future experiment in the cosmic frontier, for instance the Cosmic Explorer [23].
- Prepare to join and join one future large experiment at the regional level, like ANDES.
- Reinforce our participation in the development of computing tools, application of data science algorithms, data preservation and open science. The latter, in particular, is a leverage to boost local research in the field.

5 List of the interested scientists in the community

The country has already a good contingent of people with posgraduate training in HECAP:

- Edy Ayala (Escuela Politécnica Nacional)
- Mario Audelo (Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo)
- Lotfi Boubekeur (Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Edgar Carrera (Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Dennis Cazar (Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Ernesto Contreras (Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Mary Díaz (Universidade Estadual de Campinas)
- Alejandro Gómez (ETH Zurich)
- Daniel Guerrero (Ph.D. (c), University of Florida)
- David Hervás (Ph.D. (c), The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)
- Cristina Mantilla (Ph.D. (c) Johns Hopkins University)
- Luis Manzanillas (Max-Planck-Institute for Physics)
- Carlos Marín (Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Jorge Martínez (Ph.D. (c), Notre Dame University)
- Santiago Paredes (Ph.D. (c) University of Oxford)
- Raquel Quishpe (Ph.D. (c), University of Houston)
- Pablo Rivadeneira (Ph.D. (c), DESY, University of Hamburg)
- Stephany Vargas, (Ph.D. (c), Chiba University)
- Nicolás Vásquez (Escuela Politécnica Nacional)
- Harold Yepes Ramirez (Yachay Tech University)
- Francisco Yumiceva (Florida Institute of Technology)

There is also a lot of potential in undergraduate students or recent graduates:

- Juan David Alcivar Espin (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Lenin Wladimir Calvache Travez (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Carlos Eduardo Cocha Toapaxi (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Pablo Daniel Contreras Guerra (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Asdrubal Cruz (BSc in Physic from Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Bryan Daniel Darquea Chauca (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Felipe Navarro (BSc Physics from Universidad San Francisco de Quito)
- Genesis Marisol Mendoza Celorio (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Rony David Quinatoa Catucuago (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)
- Victor Alexander Torres Sanchez (BSc in Physics from Yachay Tech University)

6 Current status and expected challenges

The LHC accelerates protons (and heavy ions) to the the highest available energies (≈ 14 TeV). The outcome of these collisions can be studied to find out the physics of the TeV scale. The LHC accelerator and its experiments are currently going through a phase of upgrades called Long Shutdown 2 (LS2). The LS2 will last until May 2021, when it will restart.

The CMS experiment is a multipurpose detector. This cylindrical-shaped machine consists of several different technologies, arranged by layers, which are able to record the energy, momentum and position of most of the residual particles in each collision. CMS is arduously preparing for the higher luminosity environment in 2021. The higher pile-up per event constitutes the main operational challenge. Ecuadorian groups collaborating in these experiments are participating in these efforts. In particular, Ecuadorian scientists and engineers have contributed to the High Luminosity Trigger, the Beam Radiation Instrumentation and Monitoring (BRIL) subsystem and are also deeply involved in the data preservation and open access activities. Several analysis addressing top physics, Higgs physics and exotic particles searches have had Ecuadorian contributions.

KM3NeT is a large-scale research infrastructure under construction and permanent operation, consisting of a network of deep-sea neutrino telescopes (NTs) in the abyss of the Mediterranean Sea with user ports for Earth and Sea Sciences. The network of NTs are just two km^3 detection arrays: ARCA, a sparser detector for astrophysical neutrinos research; and ORCA, a denser detector for atmospheric neutrino research, both sharing the same technology and layout but dimensions scaled. Yachay Tech collaborates in PMTs technology, acoustic positioning subsystems and selection of physical events for multi-messenger astronomy. Such areas will complement near future roles in the development of an optical calibration system for KM3NeT Phase-II, commissioning of the remote operations control room at Yachay Tech and the construction of the PMTs technology lab in the Campus. Participation in associated sciences commented above is also foreseen.

The LAGO project is a particular example of collaborative work by active, individual groups, with some feedback from collaborators of large infrastructures as that mentioned above. The simple idea behind the project is to build water Cherenkov detectors (WCDs) at several cities in many countries in Latin America in order to study cosmic ray residua. Ideally, they will be located at high altitude (> 4800 m a.s.l) where, using the single particle technique, can take advantage of the larger electronic component of the cosmic rays atmospheric showers, and study spectacular events like GRB impacts. In practice, many of these devices are being optimized also for the study of space weather. In any case, LAGO has proved vital in attracting and training a whole young generation of scientists.

The Ecuadorian LAGO groups have struggled with keeping these instruments to work stably. Even though several WCDs have acquired data for important periods of time, inadequate size of the detector, electronic noise or lack of funding for replacements have limited the quality of these data. Within the financial limitations, local scientists and engineers keep working on solving these problems and training the next generation of researchers.

The common challenge for all the groups involved in the different experiments is financial. The lack of mobility funding makes all these activities harder to accomplish. Even though this has not been the case yet, the unfortunate political volatility could present future problems with the funding of the projects.

7 Timeline

8 Construction and operational costs

By the time Ecuadorian groups joined the CMS experiment, it was already built. The costs for operating the detector oscillates around 40K USD per year for the Ecuadorian State (all institutes). In addition, the contributions to the upgrades towards HL-LHC represent a similar monetary figure.

As far as the association with the KM3NeT Collaboration, the estimated cost for building the experiment (phase I and II) sits at around 270 million USD. The emerging group at Yachay Tech is looking to contribute financially to the common fund and operations costs in the short term.

The LAGO project is much more modest experiment in economical terms. The development of the needed WCDs and electronics is realized by each of the member institutes. In the case of Ecuador, the investment to build and operate mainly 3 WCDs oscillates around 15K USD.

The projects taken as examples in this document have the following ball-park amounts for their construction phases:

- DUNE: 480 million USD [24]
- FCC: 15 billion USD (specific detector costs have not been specified yet) [25]
- ANDES: 10 million USD [26]
- Cosmic Explorer: 80 million [27]

We believe that the Ecuadorian State has the capacity to support the growth of Ecuadorian research groups in HECAP and to finance their participation in some of the experiments with large international infrastructures along the lines discussed in this document. It is known that the scientific and technological returns surpass the investment.

9 Computing requirements

All the experiments mentioned in these strategy have similar computing challenges [28] due to the vast amount of events they either have to record or simulate. The sophistication of the trigger systems also impose advanced technological demands. Not only CPU capacity but also GPU availability to run parallel processing (typical of Machine Learning algorithms, for instance) will be a trend in the upcoming years. Data science methods will have to be tested, improved and implemented in order to cope with the high rate/energy data acquisition and simulation. Finally, open data, open science, and open documentation is becoming the rule among these experiments, which will help maintain the support of funding agencies.

Although scientists who work on large collaborations like CMS and KM3NeT use the computing infrastructure from each experiment (GRID computing, mostly), Ecuador has its own computing resources. Yachay Tech, for instance, profits from supercomputing infrastructure [29] in Urucuquí. At least two computer clusters will be made available to help the HECAP community.

The university corporation CEDIA [30] and USFQ [31] have also some computing resources that can be used by scientists in the field.

Furthermore, Ecuador is adhering to the common strategy adopted recently [32] in the important area of computing for these kind of experiments.

10 Conclusions and Recommendations

In recent years, Ecuadorian HECAP groups have expanded considerably and several of its physicists are being trained at the highest level either locally or abroad. There are now groups working formally with the CMS Collaboration at the LHC, the KM3NeT Collaboration and the LAGO project.

We recommend that the strategy of Ecuadorian groups working on HECAP builds up around these ongoing efforts and expand to include presence in experimental cosmology and/or astroparticle physics at the international level.

We strongly support the continuity of the LHC and HL-LHC program at CERN, in particular that of the CMS experiment. Likewise, we enthusiastically endorse the active participation of Ecuadorian groups in the KM3NeT and LAGO experiments.

In the medium/long term future, we vigorously recommend joining the experimental program of one of the next-generation accelerators, like ILC, CLIC or FCC, etc.; one of the main future experiments in the intensity frontier, like DUNE at Fermilab and/or complementary long base line future experiments (side-project within KM3NeT); an experimental program in the cosmic frontier, like CTA, LIGO or VIRGO, COSMIC EXPLORER, etc.; and a regional large collaboration, like ANDES.

Finally, we energetically encourage active participation in all related aspects of engineering, in particular software and computing efforts that derive from the involvement in these experiments, especially those related to the development and/or application of data science algorithms, and open data and open science. Additionally we will bet strongly on applied projects based on the know-how and knowledge transfer from above activities, as well as strengthen relations with government institutions and links to the private sector.

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